

The Influence of Work Culture, Discipline, and Motivation on Employee Performance Through Competence

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of work culture, discipline and motivation on employee performance through competency in the Deputy for Cyber Security and Crypto Operations of the National Cyber and Crypto Agency. The research method used is quantitative research. This study uses a saturation sample or saturated sampling, which means that the entire population in the Deputy II environment became respondents in this study with a total of 345 respondents. Data analysis uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis using the AMOS 29 tool. The analysis carried out is Validity Test, Reliability Test, SEM Assumption Test (Normality Test, Outliers Test, Multicollinearity Test), Goodness of Fit Test and Direct and Indirect Effect Test. The results of the study show that: (1) Work Culture has a positive and significant effect on Competence with a CR value of 2.464 and a probability of 0.014, (2) Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Competence with a CR value of 2.422 with a probability of 0.015, (3) Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Competence with a CR value of 3.499 with a probability of 0.001, (4) Work Culture has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a CR value of 2.032 with a probability of 0.042, (5) There is a positive and significant effect between Discipline and Employee Performance with a CR value of 2.003 and a probability of 0.045, (6) There is a positive and significant effect between Motivation and Employee Performance with a CR value of 3.021 with a probability of 0.003, and (7) There is a positive and significant effect between Competence and Employee Performance with a CR value of 2.587 with a probability of 0.010.

KEYWORDS: Work Culture, Discipline, Motivation, Competence, Employee Performance, Deputy II BSSN, SEM Assumption

INTRODUCTION

The State Cyber and Cryptography Agency (BSSN) is a government agency of the Republic of Indonesia engaged in Information Security and Cyber Security (President of the Republic of Indonesia, 2021b). BSSN is a government agency that has undergone a transformation of the merger of existing government information security institutions, namely the State Cryptography Institute (Lemsaneg) with the Directorate of Information Security, the Directorate General of Informatics Applications, the Ministry of Communication and Informatics (Kemenkominfo) through Presidential Regulation Number 53 of 2017. With the formation of BSSN, all duties and functions in the field of Cryptography in Lemsaneg as well as the implementation of duties and functions in the field of information security, securing the use of telecommunication networks within the scope of the Ministry of Communication and Information are carried out by BSSN.

With the transformation of Lemsaneg into BSSN, it has an impact on resources within the scope of BSSN. Changes in duties and functions, changes in the work environment, work culture, and employee competencies that have an impact on BSSN performance results. Of course, it is a challenge for BSSN as a new government agency in an effort to manage cyber and password security on a national scale. To manage cyber security and cryptography on a national scale, BSSN needs to manage human resources (HR) because it is the main milestone in handling cyber and cryptography nationally.

As a government agency, BSSN has a vision of becoming a trusted institution in maintaining state cyber and cryptography by synergizing various stakeholders to participate in realizing national security and increasing national economic growth (Head of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency, 2020). And one of BSSN's missions is to provide and optimize cybersecurity and password resources through a continuous learning and quality improvement process supported by transparent and accountable office management.

BSSN is assisted by several work units in an effort to carry out organizational duties and functions. The work units include: Main Secretariat, Deputy for Cybersecurity and Cryptography Strategy and Policy, Deputy for Cybersecurity and Cryptography Operations, Deputy for Cybersecurity and Cryptography for Government and Human Development, Deputy for Cybersecurity and Cryptography for the Economy, Inspectorate, Cybersecurity and Cryptography Certification Center, Data and Information Communication Technology Center, Human Resource Development Center, and Technical Implementation Unit (Head of the State

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Cyber and Cryptography Agency, 2023a). The Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations was formed in August 2021 after undergoing a reorganization. And since 2022 until now, Deputy Officials II have undergone 1 change. Leading officials with military backgrounds, so the implementation of cyber security and cryptography operations is widely adopted from the military world. Meanwhile, the human resources in Deputy II are all civil servants and graduates from the State Cyber and Cryptography Polytechnic (SSN Polytechnic), so adjustments and adaptations to the work culture within Deputy II are needed.

In addition to the influence of work culture in Deputy II BSSN, discipline is another important factor to achieve organizational performance targets. Human resources in the Deputy II environment who come from SSN/STSN Polytechnic graduates have been equipped with disciplinary knowledge when undergoing boarding lectures for four years by instilling values, norms and culture that are adapted to the work culture at BSSN. Thus, the Human Resources of Deputy II has been able to carry out work with good discipline. Apart from SSN Polytechnic graduates, Deputy II HR also comes from the TNI for structural positions, the opening of general CPNS to Government Employees with Employment Agreements (PPPK). The following are statistics on employee discipline data in the last three years.

In the world of work, discipline is an important factor in efforts to achieve organizational performance targets, especially in government agencies. With the formation of a good discipline culture, it has an impact on a good work environment and has an impact on the achievement of organizational performance.

To be able to achieve the level of discipline desired by the organization, the organization needs to pay attention to every employee, namely the motivation aspect. Often, employees experience demotivation caused by various things, such as an unsupportive work environment, having a different work culture with leaders with military backgrounds, unhealthy competition from colleagues, and so on. Thus, it has an impact on the achievement of organizational performance that is not in accordance with the targets that have been set. Management plays an important role in maintaining motivation in every employee in the organization so that employees always have high motivation and willingness to work and learn in the organization they are occupied. Motivation is not just about giving aphorisms or quotes, but motivation must be embedded in each employee that motivation can have an impact both on the employee himself and directly on the organization he or she is occupied.

In improving employee performance in an organization, the motivation aspect is another important factor. Motivation is a process that influences a person to get what they want both positively and negatively (Wahyudi & Tupti, 2019). In an effort to increase employee motivation, organizations make various efforts to improve employee performance, one of which is by looking at the motivation aspect. Every year, the number of BSSN employees fluctuates. This is because every year BSSN accepts graduates of the State Cyber and Cryptography Polytechnic after taking a four-year boarding education located in Ciseeng, Bogor Regency. With the entry of SSN Polytechnic graduates every year in large numbers, it has an impact on old employees who work in the Deputy to undergo mutations to other work units. So, the business process that has been carried out must adapt again to new employees who have graduated from the SSN Polytechnic. In addition, BSSN also opens formations for certain employee positions both through the opening of CPNS and PPPK.

Talking about the performance of organizational employees, it is inseparable from the achievements or targets of the organization. High-performing employees will make a great and positive contribution to achieving organizational success. Including Deputy II also has organizational achievement targets. The graph shows that employee performance has declined in 2021. In the graph, it is stated that in 2021 the performance value of Deputy II reached 124% because at that time there was a reorganization in the BSSN environment so that the assessment was based on the nomenclature of the old work unit to the new work unit (Plt. Deputy for Cyber Security and Password Operations, 2021). Then, in 2022, the performance value of Deputy II reached 108.74%, a decrease in 2021 because Deputy II is still in the process of transferring duties and authority in carrying out activities at BSSN (Deputy for Cyber Security and Password Operations, 2022). And in 2023, the performance value of Deputy II reached 106.45%, a decrease of 2.29% (Deputy for Cyber Security and Password Operations, 2023a). In addition, it is also caused by increasing work in the Deputy II environment which is not proportional to the portion of work of each employee. So, this is a special concern regarding improving performance within the Deputy II of BSSN.

Based on the background described, employee performance can be influenced by several variables, including: work culture, discipline, motivation and competence. The research will be carried out in the work unit of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Password Operations, BSSN. Therefore, the performance of Deputy II employees can certainly be associated with this factor

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literally, the word management comes from the ancient French language *ménagement*, which means the art of executing and organizing. Management is a science and art in regulating the process of utilizing human resources and other resources effectively and efficiently to achieve a certain goal (M. S. P. Hasibuan, 2011). Another opinion also explains that management is also interpreted as planning, implementing, and supervising organizational resources to achieve goals effectively and efficiently (H. Usman, 2013). In addition, management is the process of using resources effectively to achieve goals (Lukman, 1995). Management is defined as the process of providing work direction to everyone in an organization to achieve certain goals (Meithiana & Ansory, 2018).

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Management can also be interpreted as an art to understand what to do and how the easiest and cheapest way to do it as best as possible (Terry, 2021). Management can also be understood in organizations to achieve organizational goals, with the management of organizational resources (Prihatini & Dewi, 2021). From various meanings, Management can be interpreted as an art in managing an organization consisting of planning, implementation and supervision to achieve goals to be achieved together.

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a management process in determining the direction of the movement of organizational human resources from future positions, while HR is a set of processes and activities that are carried out jointly with HR management and line managers to solve organizational problems associated with humans (Mahriza et al., 2023). In addition, HR Management can be interpreted as activities or activities such as recruitment, appointment, training, development, and compensation for all types of workforce (Pratama et al., 2022). HR management can refer to the activities of staff specialists who are responsible for the goals of employees in the organization. To manage human resources in an organization, the Head of the Human Resources Department is needed who is responsible for building and implementing strategies to improve the quality of human resources in the organization (Tampubolon, 2016). Another opinion states that HR Management is a policy and practice involved in implementing the human resources aspect of a management position, including recruitment, screening, training, awards, and others (Dessler, 2015). HR management can also be said to be a key function in an organization, having an important role in managing organizational human resources, starting from the recruitment phase to development, awards to and performance management (Darmawan et al., 2023). From various definitions of HR Management, it can be interpreted that HR Management is a management process that determines the future direction of the organization's human resources and involves several activities such as recruitment, appointment, training, development, and labor compensation.

Work Culture is a mental attitude that always seeks to improve and improve what has been achieved, by applying new methods and being confident in the progress obtained (Hatalea et al., 2014). Culture provides identity for organizational employees and generates a commitment to beliefs and values that are greater than themselves (Sedarmayanti & Rahadian, 2018). Work culture is a philosophy based on a view of life as a value that becomes a trait, habit, and driver that is cultivated in a group and reflected in attitudes into behavior (M. A. R. Siregar et al., 2020). In building culture, it means improving and maintaining the positive side and trying to get used to certain patterns of behavior in order to create a new and better form (Halim, 2021). Work culture is a philosophical statement that functions as an important requirement for an employee because it can be interpreted formally in various rules from each organization (Putri et al., 2023). Work culture will be fulfilled if employees are actors in an organization so that elements that affect performance can be created perfectly (Moron et al., 2023). Based on the description above, it can be said that work culture is a philosophy of life as a value that changes into traits and habits carried out in an organization.

Work discipline is an attitude of self-control to obey the regulations that have been given by the organization in order to achieve goals (Jufrizen & Hadi, 2021). In addition, discipline is an organizational expectation, about how work runs well, without any risks and adverse negative impacts (Wahyudi, 2019). Awareness in implementing organizational rules reflected in discipline work will also increase the high performance of employees (Ekhsan, 2019). Discipline also shows the respect that an employee has for the rules and regulations in the organization (Adinda et al., 2023). Discipline can also be interpreted as a training that aims to improve attitudes, shape employee behavior so that the employee voluntarily tries to work cooperatively with other employees to improve work performance (Dandu, 2019). The application of discipline is by taking action against employees who commit an act of irregularity and violate organizational regulations that have an impact on the organization's reputation. Regarding discipline in Government Agencies, it is stated that Civil Servant Discipline is the ability of civil servants to obey their obligations and avoid prohibitions specified in laws and regulations (President of the Republic of Indonesia, 2021a). Based on the description of the definition of discipline, it can be concluded that discipline is an attitude of employees in obeying the rules that apply in the organization to achieve organizational goals.

Work motivation is an encouragement and stimulation that causes individuals to be enthusiastic about work (Rosmaini & Tanjung, 2019). In addition, motivation is a factor that causes enthusiasm or work encouragement in individual employees to do something in order to obtain what is needed by employees and achieve organizational goals (Hutajulu et al., 2021). Motivation can also be interpreted as a form of willingness to spend the highest effort to achieve organizational goals, which is conditioned by the ability to meet the individual needs of employees (Farisi et al., 2020). Motivation is a process that shows a person's intensity, direction and perseverance from efforts towards achieving goals (Suwatno & Priansa D.J, 2011). Motivation can be interpreted as a resource force that moves and controls human behavior (Sutanjar & Saryono, 2019). Motivation is a desire that arises in a person because they are inspired, enthusiastic, and encouraged to carry out activities with sincerity, and sincerity so that the output of the activities carried out gets quality results (Afandi, 2018). Based on the definition of motivation from, it can be concluded that work motivation is an encouragement from an employee to achieve certain goals in the hope of getting good and quality results.

Competence is the ability to do a job based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude demanded by a job (Anggriawan et al., 2023). In addition, competence can be interpreted as an effective behavioral device related to exploration and investigation, analyzing, thinking and paying attention that leads to individuals finding ways to achieve certain goals effectively and efficiently (Fauzi, 2019). In addition, competence can be interpreted as a fundamental characteristic that a person possesses that has

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a direct influence on, or can predict excellent performance (Sedarmayanti, 2016). Competence can be defined as individuals who have better, more effective, and more consistent performance than individuals who have average performance and even do not have competence in carrying out their work (Mulia & Saputra, 2021). In addition, work competence is the work ability of each individual which includes aspects of knowledge, skills, and work attitudes in accordance with the set standards (President of the Republic of Indonesia, 2003). Broadly speaking, competence is one of the important elements in supporting employee performance in an organization. Employees who have good and qualified abilities can accelerate organizational achievements and organizations can grow and develop to face increasingly rapid global competition (Heri & Andayani, 2021). Based on the description of the definition, it can be concluded that competence is the ability possessed by a person to be applied in the context of self-development and contribute to the development of an organization.

Employee performance is the result achieved by an employee according to the applicable measure, in a certain period of time, which is related to the work and the behavior and actions of an employee (Adnyana & Ajeng Gemellia, 2021). In addition, performance can also be defined as the results or outputs of the implementation of work, both physical and non-physical, which during the implementation of tasks are based on the job description and assessed within a certain period of time (I. Usman, 2022). Employee performance is related to the final result of an employee's work activity in the organization, which is reflected in the output produced both in terms of quantity and quality (Sarumaha, 2022). Then, performance is also defined as a function of motivation and the ability to complete the tasks or work of an employee who has a certain level of ability (Pusparani, 2021). Performance can also be interpreted as an achievement of the results of work achieved by individuals in carrying out their duties and responsibilities (Fransiska & Tupti, 2020). Performance also requires a person to behave in accordance with organizational regulations and must show good results (Sutoro et al., 2020).

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used in this study is in the form of a quantitative method. Quantitative research methods can be described as research methods used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make generalized conclusions or generalizations (Ramdhan, 2021). Research methodology is generally understood as a scientific activity that is carried out in stages starting with determining the topic, collecting data and analyzing the data, so that later an understanding and understanding of a certain topic, symptom or issue is obtained. It is said to be 'gradual' because this activity takes place following a certain process, so there are steps that need to be passed in stages before moving on to the next stage. This study leads to research related to Work Culture, Discipline and Motivation that affects Employee Performance through Employee Competency at the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations, State Cyber and Cryptography Agency.

The research uses an associative research approach. Associative research is research that aims to find out the relationship between two or more variables. So associative research is research whose purpose is to find out the relationship between two or more variables. Where the relationship between variables in this study will be analyzed using the relevant statistical formula on the data to test the hypothesis (Ghadani et al., 2022). This research requires guidelines and techniques in conducting research planning that aims to be a guide in building strategies that produce research models. The type of design of this research is Survey Research, which is quantitative research based on the results of a survey on an individual or group in an organization. A research design is an investigation plan that is prepared in such a way that the researcher will be able to obtain answers to the researcher's questions (Murjani, 2022). The research design must be in accordance with the research objectives so that what has been designed to answer the problem formulation can be achieved with the purpose of the research. The variables that we want to find the relationship between one variable and the other variables are Work Culture (X1), Discipline (X2), Motivation (X3), Employee Performance (Y) and Competency (Z).

TEST RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

The test of this research instrument will be explained related to the results of validity and reliability tests based on the results of data processing using SEM-AMOS version 29. 1) Validity Test Validity is an index that shows that the measuring tool used actually measures what will be measured (Amanda et al., 2019). The higher the validity of the instrument, the more accurate the measuring instrument measures a data. The validity test is carried out by paying attention to the value of the factor loading standard or the standard estimation standard of each indicator. If the value of the standard loading factor ≥ 0.5 , it is declared valid (Wijanto, 2008) (Haryono, 2017). 2) Reliability Test Reliability is a measure of the internal consistency indicator. The high reliability results ensure that individual indicators are all consistent with their measurements (Haryono, 2017). A reliable questionnaire is if the respondent's answers are stable or consistent and have a generally acceptable construct reliability (CR) value of ≥ 0.7 and the average value of the extracted variant (Average Variance Extracted / AVE) ≥ 0.5 (Haryono & Wardoyo, 2012)

Assumption Test Structural Equation Model (SEM)

Structural Equation Modelling or SEM is a set of statistical techniques with the possibility of testing a series of relatively complex relationships in stages (Haryono, 2017). In addition, the SEM method is a development of path analysis and gandy regression which

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is a form of multivariate analysis model. The SEM assumption test is a stage of SEM analysis that is required to meet assumptions such as normality, outliers, and multicollinearity (residual value). Normality Test Estimation with Maximum Likelihood allows the observed variable to meet the assumption of multivariate normality. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct tests to see the level of normality in a multivariate manner to the data used in this study. The test was carried out by observing the kurtosis value of the data used. The evaluation of multivariate normality with SEM-AMOS version 29 was carried out with the criterion of critical ratio (CR) of multivariate in curtosis, if it is in the range between ± 2.58 (at a significance level of 1% or 0.01), it means that the data is normally distributed in a multivariate manner. That is, it can be concluded that the distributed data is normal if the critical ratio (CR) value of the multivariate in curtosis is in the range between ± 2.58 (Ghozali, 2008). Test Outliers Outlier can be interpreted as data that has unique characteristics, which looks far different from other data that appears in the form of extreme values, applicable to univariate and multivariate (Sugiono et al., 2021). The Outlier Test is a test to find out data that has different characteristics (Ovaliana & Mahfudz, 2022). The basis for detecting multivariate outliers is with Mahalanobis Distance (Filzmoser, 2004). The standard method for multivariate outlier detection is a robust parameter estimation in Mahalanobis Distance that takes into account the covariance matrix and its comparison with the critical value of the χ^2 distribution (Barus & Suterman, 2023). Observations of data that are far from their centroid values are considered outlier and should be discarded from the analysis. The criteria used are based on the Chi-Squares value in the degree of freedom, namely the number of indicators in the fit model of the research at a significance level of $p \leq 0.001$ (Haryono & Wardoyo, 2012). Multicollinearity Test Then, a multicollinearity test was carried out. This test aims to see if there is multicollinearity and singularity in a multivariate. In the test using SEM-AMOS version 29, the residual value test can be seen from the unstandardized residual, a data is stated to have a large residual value if the unstandardized residual value > 0.9 .

Evaluation Criteria Goodness of Fit

The Goodness of Fit criterion aims to determine the suitability of the research model, by assessing whether the processed data has met the assumptions of the proposed structural equation model. These assumptions include: Meet the criteria for the minimum number of samples, which is 100; The assumption of normality is fulfilled by looking at the critical ratio (CR) value; There is no outlier, where the observation of a data that has unique characteristics and looks very different from other data observations; The likelihood of multicollinearity and singularity (a combination of linear and variable analyzed). If the criteria from SEM are met, then several criteria in goodness of fit are determined to determine the feasibility in the research model used. The criteria that need to be met in goodness of fit include: 1) The Minimum Sample Discrepancy Function (CMIN/DF) is a measure obtained from the chi-square value divided by the degree of freedom. This index is a parsimonious fit index that measures the relationship between the goodness of fit model and the number of estimated coefficients expected to achieve the level of conformity. The recommended value for accepting a model's conformity is $CMIN/DF \leq 2.0$. 2) Goodness of Fit Index (GFI). This index reflects the calculated degree of model fit from the squared residual of the predicted model compared to the actual data. The GFI ranges from 0 to 1 with criteria ≥ 0.80 good fit and $0.80 \leq GFI < 0.80$ marginal fit. 3) Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is a development of GFI, which has been adjusted to the ratio of the degree of freedom of the proposed model to the degree of freedom of null model (a single construction model with all construction measurement indicators). The recommended value is $AGFI > 0.80$. The AGFI ranges from 0 to 1.0 with criteria ≥ 0.80 good fit and $0.80 \leq TLI < 0.90$ marginal fit. 4) Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is an index used to measure the suitability of the model replacing the chi-square statistic in a large number of samples. An RMSEA value of ≤ 0.08 indicates a good index to accept the suitability of the model with a criterion of $0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.08$ good fit; $0.08 - 0.10$ marginal fit, and ≥ 0.10 poor fit. 5) Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is an incremental fit index, which compares the tested model with a null model. This index is excellent for measuring the acceptance rate of a model, because like CMIN/DF, the value is not affected by the sample size. The index value is in the range from 0 to 1 and a value close to 1 indicates that the model has a good level of fit. The recommended admission score is $CFI \geq 0.90$. A CFI value of > 0.90 indicates a good fit while $0.80 < CFI < 0.90$, which is a marginal fit. 6) The Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) is an incremental fit that compares the tested model with the null model. This conformity index is less affected by the sample size. The recommended admission score is $TLI \geq 0.90$. As for the criteria, ≥ 0.90 good fit and $0.80 \leq TLI < 0.90$ marginal fit.

Testing Hypothesis

When the criteria for the estimated goodness of fit structural model have been declared to be eligible, the next stage is to conduct an analysis of the hypothesis test. The hypothesis test was carried out to determine whether or not there was an influence of independent variables on dependent variables on research variables. The decision on whether or not the indicator variable is significant can be made by comparing the p-value value with the selected significance level (α). The amount of α value is conventionally set at 5% (0.05). If the critical ratio (CR) value is greater than 1.96, the variable is said to be significant and if it is smaller, it is not significant, which means that if the p-value ≤ 0.05 , the indicator variable is said to be significant, while if the p-value > 0.05 , the indicator variable is said to be insignificant.

RESULTS

In this study, there are two exogenous variables, namely Competency (Z) and Employee Performance (Y). Then the results of the

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Exogenous CFA test in this study can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 4. 1 Endogenous CFA Test Results

Based on figure 4.9 above, the endogenous model in this study consists of two variables, namely Competence (Z) and Employee Performance (Y). Goodness of fit model that can be measured with Significance Probability, CMIN/DIF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI criteria. The results of the Goodness of Fit Model test can be seen in the table below.

Table 4. 1 Goodness of Fit Model Endogen

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Nilai Indeks	Evaluasi
Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,239	Good Fit
CMIN/DF	$< 2,00$	1,075	Good Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,80$	0,951	Good Fit
AGFI	$\geq 0,80$	0,939	Good Fit
RMSEA	$< 0,08$	0,015	Good Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0,996	Good Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,997	Good Fit

Based on Table 4.1 above, the Goodness of Fit Model Endogenous as measured by the criteria of Significance Probability, CMIN/DIF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI all index values meet the cutt-off value requirements with fit evaluation

Figure 4. 2 Full Model

Based on Figure 4.2 above, the full model in this study has five variables consisting of Work Culture (X1), Discipline (X2), Motivation (X3), Competency (Z), and Employee Performance (Y). Goodness of Fit in the Full Model is measured by the criteria of Significance Probability, CMIN/DF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI. The results of the Goodness of Fit Model test can be seen in the table below.

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Table 4. 2 Goodness of Fit Full Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Nilai Indeks	Evaluasi
Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,026	Marginal Fit
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	1,068	Good Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,80$	0,860	Good Fit
AGFI	$\geq 0,80$	0,849	Good Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,014	Good Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0,991	Good Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,991	Good Fit

Based on Table 4.2 above, the Goodness of Fit Full Model measured by the criteria of Significance Probability, CMIN/DF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI all index values meet the cutt-off value requirements with fit evaluation. Because all the criteria have been met so that further analysis can be carried out.

Direct Effect Test

The determination of variables is considered significant or cannot be seen by comparing the p-value with the selected level of significance (α). The α value is conventionally set at 5% (0.05). Furthermore, if the t-calculated value in the Critical Ratio (CR) is greater than 1.96 then the variable is said to be significant (H_a is accepted) and if there is no then it is not significant (H_o is accepted), the same is true if the p-value ≤ 0.05 then the variable is said to be significant (H_a is accepted), while if the p-value ≥ 0.05 then the variable is said to be insignificant (H_o is accepted).

Table 4. 3 Results of the Direct Influence Hypothesis Test

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
K	<---	BK	0,169	0,069	2,464	0,014	par_4
K	<---	D	0,187	0,077	2,422	0,015	par_5
K	<---	M	0,202	0,058	3,499	***	par_6
KP	<---	K	0,126	0,049	2,587	0,010	par_7
KP	<---	BK	0,116	0,057	2,032	0,042	par_8
KP	<---	D	0,128	0,064	2,003	0,045	par_9
P	--		0,147	0,049	3,021	0,003	par_10

Based on Table 4.21 above regarding the results of the direct influence hypothesis test, it can be concluded that among others: a) The Influence of Work Culture on Competence Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Work Culture on the Competency of BSSN Deputy II Employees produces a CR value with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 2.464 and a probability value of 0.014. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. This means that it can be concluded that Work Culture has a significant positive effect on Competence. b) The Effect of Discipline on Competence Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Discipline on the Competency of BSSN Deputy II Employees resulted in a CR value of 2.422 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.000. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Discipline has a significant positive effect on Competence. c) The Effect of Motivation on Competence Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Motivation on Competency produces a CR value of 3.499 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.000. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Motivation has a significant positive effect on Competence. d) The Influence of Work Culture on Employee Performance Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Work Culture on Employee Performance produces a CR value of 2.032 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.042. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Work Culture has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance. e) The Effect of Discipline on Employee Performance Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Discipline on Employee Performance produces a CR value of 2.003 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.045. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Discipline has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance. f) The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Motivation on Employee Performance produces a CR value of 3.021 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.003. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Motivation has a significant positive effect on Employee

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Performance. g) The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance Based on Table 4.21, it is known that the influence of Competence on Employee Performance produces a CR value of 2.587 with a positive value (+) and a probability value of 0.010. Based on these results, it is known that the CR value is greater than 1.96 and the probability is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that Competence has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance

Indirect Effect Test

The Effect of the Competency Variable (Z) Mediating the Work Culture Variable (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) To calculate the indirect influence, it must be calculated manually because SEM-AMOS does not produce a significant output of indirect influence. The mediation hypothesis test was carried out with the Sobel test developed by Sobel. The sobel test was carried out by testing the strength of the indirect effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) through the mediating variable (Z). So the magnitude of the standard error of indirect effect S_{ab} based on the estimate and standard error values in the table, the values of each variable are obtained as follows: $a = 0.169$ {Coefficient of estimate direct effect of the Work Culture variable (X1) on the Competency variable (Z)} $b = 0.126$ {Estimate coefficient direct effect of the Competency variable (Z) on the Employee Performance variable (Y)} $S_a = 0.069$ (Standard Error of a) $S_b = 0.049$ (Standard Error of b) So it can be confirmed by calculating the Sobel Test Calculator as follows:

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.169	Sobel test: 1.77351132	0.01200669	0.07614402
b	0.126	Aroian test: 1.70711963	0.01247364	0.08779982
s_a	0.069	Goodman test: 1.84830494	0.01152083	0.06455824
s_b	0.049	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 4. 3 Sobel Test Output 1

(Source: <https://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>, processed 2024) Based on the results of the sobel test in Figure 4.11, it shows a sobel value of 1.773 with a positive value and a probability value of 0.076 which is smaller than 1.96 and greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that Competence (Z) is not able to mediate the influence between Work Culture (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) positively and significantly.

The Effect of the Competency Variable (Z) Mediating the Discipline Variable (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) To calculate the indirect influence, it must be calculated manually because SEM-AMOS does not produce a significant output of indirect influence. The mediation hypothesis test was carried out with the Sobel test developed by Sobel. The sobel test was carried out by testing the strength of the indirect effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) through the mediating variable (Z). So the magnitude of the standard error of indirect effect S_{ab} based on the estimate and standard error values in the table, the values of each variable are obtained as follows: $a = 0.187$ {Coefficient of estimate direct effect of the Discipline variable (X2) on the Competency variable (Z)} $b = 0.126$ {Estimate coefficient direct effect of the Competency variable (Z) on the Employee Performance variable (Y)} $S_a = 0.077$ (Standard Error of a) $S_b = 0.049$ (Standard Error of b) So it can be confirmed by calculating the Sobel Test Calculator as follows:

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.187	Sobel test: 1.76560337	0.01334501	0.07746241
b	0.126	Aroian test: 1.69900396	0.01386813	0.08931844
s_a	0.077	Goodman test: 1.84070348	0.01280054	0.06566502
s_b	0.049	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 4. 4 Sobel Test Results 2

(Source: <https://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>, processed 2024) Based on the results of the sobel test in Figure 4.12, it shows a sobel value of 1.765 with a positive value and a probability value of 0.077 which is smaller than 1.96 and greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that Competency (Z) is not able to mediate the influence between Discipline (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) positively and significantly.

The Effect of the Competency Variable (Z) Mediating the Motivation Variable (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) To calculate the indirect influence, it must be calculated manually because SEM-AMOS does not produce a significant output of indirect influence. The mediation hypothesis test was carried out with the Sobel test developed by Sobel. The sobel test was carried out by testing the strength of the indirect effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) through the mediating variable (Z). So the magnitude of the standard error of indirect effect S_{ab} based on the estimate and standard error values in the table, the values of each variable are obtained as follows: $a = 0.202$ {Coefficient of estimate direct effect of the Motivation variable (X3) on the Competency variable (Z)} $b = 0.126$ {Estimate coefficient direct effect of the Competency variable (Z) on the Employee

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Performance variable (Y)} $S_a = 0.058$ (Standard Error of a) $S_b = 0.049$ (Standard Error of b) So it can be confirmed by calculating the Sobel Test Calculator as follows:

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.202	Sobel test: 2.06867175	0.01230355	0.0385769
b	0.126	Aroian test: 2.01559786	0.01262752	0.04384204
s_a	0.058	Goodman test: 2.12617182	0.01197081	0.03348896
s_b	0.049	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 4. 5 Sobel Test Results 3

Based on the results of the sobel test in Figure 4.13, it shows a sobel value of 2.068 with a positive value and a probability value of 0.038 which is greater than 1.96 and less than 0.05. So it can be concluded that Competency (Z) is able to mediate the influence between Motivation (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) positively and significantly

Based on the findings in this study related to the results of direct and indirect influences that have been described earlier, a combined model and table of research findings can be made as follows:

Figure 4. 6 Model Research Findings (Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024)

Based on Table 4.23 and Figure 4.14 above, it can be concluded that the greatest direct influence on the Competency (Z) variable from the highest to the lowest is the Discipline (X2), Work Culture (X1), and Motivation (X3) variables. Then the biggest influence on the Performance (Y) variable from the highest to the lowest is the variables of Discipline (X2), Work Culture (X1), Motivation (X3) and Competency (Z). Meanwhile, when comparing the value of direct influence and indirect influence, it can be concluded that there are exogenous to endogenous variables through intervening variables that do not have an indirect influence on the Work Culture (Y) variable, namely the Work Culture variable (X1) and the Discipline variable (X2). However, the Competency variable (Z) has an indirect influence on the Work Culture variable (Y), namely the Motivation variable (X3).

CONCLUSION

The conclusion in the study with the title, "The Influence of Work Culture, Discipline, and Motivation on Employee Performance through Competency in Employees of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency, produced several research findings in the form of: 1. There is a positive and significant influence of work culture on competence in BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 2.464 and a probability of 0.014. 2. There is a positive and significant influence between discipline on competence in BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 2.422 and a probability of 0.015. 3. There was a positive and significant influence between motivation and competence in BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 3.499 and a probability of 0.001. 4. There is a positive and significant influence of work culture on the performance of BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 2.032 and a probability of 0.042. 5. There is a positive/negative and significant influence between discipline on the performance of BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 2.003 and a probability of 0.045. 6. There was a positive and significant influence between motivation on the performance of BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 3.021 and a probability of 0.003. 7. There is a positive/negative and significant influence between competence on the performance of BSSN Deputy II employees with a CR value of 2.587 and a probability of 0.010.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Abubakar, R. R. T. (2018). The Effect of Employee Competence on the Work Productivity of Employees of the Bandung City Health Office. *Journal of State Administration*, 24(1), 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.33509/Jan.V24i1.63>
- 2) Adha, R. N., Qomariah, N., & Hafidzi, A. H. (2019). The Influence of Work Motivation, Work Environment, and Work Culture on the Performance of Employees of the Jember Regency Social Service. *Journal of Science and Technology Research*, 4(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.32528/Ipteks.V4i1.2109>
- 3) Adinda, T. N., Firdaus, M. A., & Agung, S. (2023). The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance of Pt. Antam Tbk (Uibpei) Pongkor. *Indonesian Journal Of Innovation Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 134–143. <https://doi.org/10.31004/Ijim.V1i3.15>
- 4) Adnyana, I. M., & Ajeng Gemellia, A. D. (2021). Analysis of the Performance of State Civil Apparatus in the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency in 2019. *Populist : Journal of Social and Humanities*, 6(2), 211–235. <https://doi.org/10.47313/Pjsh.V6i2.1387>
- 5) Afandi, P. (2018). Concept & Indicator Human Resources Management For Management Research. *Uin Suska Riau*, 13(1).
- 6) Ali, H., Sastrodiharjo, I., & Saputra, F. (2022). Measurement of Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Workload, Work Culture and Motivation (Literature Review Study). *Jim: Journal of Multidisciplinary Science*, 1(1), 2829–4599. <https://doi.org/10.38035/Jim.V1i1>
- 7) Amanda, L., Yanuar, F., & Devianto, D. (2019). Test the validity and reliability of the level of political participation of the people of Padang City. *Journal of Mathematics Unand*, 8(1), 179. <https://doi.org/10.25077/Jmu.8.1.179-188.2019>
- 8) Amiruddin, A., Nugroho, H., Sulaiman, S., Iljasmadi, I., Wahyuni, N., Fata, N., Ismail, J. K., Helendra, H., Johan, H., Widayati, I. A., Pasaribu, P. N., Siregar, P., Mulyana, S., Balukh, S. D., Sungkawati, E., Sartika, D., Ummami, W., Rinda, R. T., & Padakari, S. (2022). *Introduction to Management (Theoretical Concepts and Approaches)* (H. Hartini, Ed.; First, Vol. 1). Cv. Indonesian Science Media.
- 9) . Anggriawan, B. S., Rusdianti, E., & Santoso, D. (2023). The Effect of Competence, Training and Compensation on the Performance of Employees with Affective Commitment as an Intervening Variable at the Public Works and Spatial Planning Office of Demak Regency. *Journal of Economic and Business Research*, 16(1), 48–67. <https://doi.org/10.26623/Jreb.V16i1.6397>
- 10) Anisa, C., & Rahmatullah, R. (2020). Vision and Mission According to Fred R. David Islamic Education Perspective. *Evaluation: Journal of Islamic Education Management*, 4(1), 70–87. <https://doi.org/10.32478/Evaluasi.V4i1.356>
- 11) Barus, F. M., & Suterman. (2023). Detecting Outliers in Multivariate Data Using the Mahalanobis-Minimum Covariance Determinant (MMCD) Distance Method. *Ijm: Indonesian Journal Of Multidisciplinary*, 1(3). <https://journal.csspublishing/index.php/Ijm> Collier, J. E. (2020). *Applied Structural Equation Modeling Using Amos*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003018414>
- 12) Dandu, S. (2019). The Influence of Recruitment, Competence, Motivation, Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the West Halmahera Regency Government. *Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Applications*, 1(2), 104–118. <https://doi.org/10.37476/Massaro.V1i2>
- 13) Darmawan, D., Retnowati, E., Halizah, S. N., Issalillah, F., Khayru, R. K., Hardyansah, R., & Putra, A. R. (2023). A study on the influence of competitive advantage and human resource management on company performance. *Journal Of Management And Economics Research*, 1(3), 77–85.
- 14) Deputy for Cybersecurity and Password Operations. (2022). Performance Report of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations for the 2022 Fiscal Year.
- 15) Deputy for Cybersecurity and Password Operations. (2023a). Performance Report of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations for the 2023 Fiscal Year.
- 16) Deputy for Cybersecurity and Password Operations. (2023b). Strategic Plan of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations 2021 to 2024.
- 17) Dessler, G. (2015). *Human Resource Management*. In *Atlas Of Cardiac Surgical Techniques (Second)*. Salemba Four.
- 18) Dewi, N. L. P. A., Endiana, I. D. M., & Arizona, I. P. E. (2019). The effect of liquidity ratio, leverage ratio and profitability ratio on financial distress in manufacturing companies. *Collection of Accounting Student Research Results (Kharisma)*, 1(1), 322–333.
- 19) Efendi, S., & Nandarini, L. (2020). Analysis Of The Influence Of Leadership Style, Training, And Physical Work Environment On Motivation And Impact On The Performance Of National Cyber And Crypto Agency Employees. *Focus*, 1(1), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.37010/Fcs.V1i1.269>
- 20) Ekhsan, M. (2019). The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance at Pt. Syncrum Logistics. *Optimal : Journal of Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.33558/Optimal.V13i1.1734>

The Influence of Work Culture, Discipline, and Motivation on Employee Performance Through Competence

- 21) Farisi, S., Irnawati, J., & Fahmi, M. (2020). The influence of motivation and work discipline on employee performance. *Journal of Humanities : Journal of Social, Economic and Legal Sciences*, 4(1), 15–33. <https://doi.org/10.30601/Humaniora.V4i1.420>
- 22) Fauzi, A. (2019). The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance in the Government and Cooperation Bureau of the Regional Secretariat of West Java Province. *Politicon: Journal of Political Science*, 1(1), 88–103. <https://doi.org/10.15575/Politicon.V1i1.5367>
- 23) Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Management Research Methods: Research Guidelines for Thesis Writing and Management Science Dissertation*.
- 24) Filzmoser, P. (2004). A Multivariate Outlier Detection Method.
- 25) Seventh International Conference On Computer Data Analysis And Modeling, 1(1989).
- 26) Fitriani, D., Foeh, J. E. H. J., & Manafe, H. A. (2022). The Influence of Competence, Motivation, and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Literature Review of Human Resource Management). *Jmpis (Journal of Educational Management and Social Sciences)*, 3(2), 981–994. <https://doi.org/10.38035/Jmpis.V3i2>
- 27) Fransiska, Y., & Tupti, Z. (2020). The Influence of Communication, Workload and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at the Population and Civil Registration Office of North Labuhanbatu. *Manegggio: Scientific Journal of Masters in Management*, 3(2), 224–234. <https://doi.org/10.30596/Manegggio.V3i2.5041>
- 28) Ghadani, A., Muhar, A. M., & Sari, A. I. (2022). The Influence of Brand Ambassador and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions on Shopee with Brand Awareness Mediation. *Insight Management Journal*, 2(3), 110–118.
- 29) Ghozali, I. (2008). *Structural Equation Model: Concept and Application with the Amos 16.0 Program*. Diponegoro University Publishing Board.
- 30) Ghozali, I. (2017). The Effect of Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction and Work Ability on Employee Performance at the Office of the Ministry of Religion of Banjar Regency. *Scientific Journal of Business Economics*, 3(1), 130–137. <https://doi.org/10.35972/Jieb.V3i1.59>
- 31) Halim, A. (2021). The Influence of Work Culture, Motivation and Discipline on Employee Performance at the Office of Food Crops, Horticulture and Animal Husbandry of Mamuju Regency. *Journal Of Economic, Management And Accounting*, 1(3), 31–41.
- 32) Hamsinah, H. (2019). The Influence Of Work Placement, Career Paths And Employee Loyalty On Employee Performance At The Public Works Department Of South Tangerang City. *Journal of Khazanah Ulum Sharia Economics (Jkues)*, 3(2), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.56184/Jkues.V3i2.139>
- 33) Hanafi, A. S., Almy, C., & Siregar, M. T. (2018). The Influence of Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Employee Performance. *Journal of Industrial Management and Logistics*, 2(1), 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.30988/Jmil.V2i1.25>
- 34) Haryono, S. (2017). *Sem Method for Management Research with Amos Lisrel Pls*. Luxima Metro Media, 450.
- 35) Haryono, S., & Wardoyo, P. (2012). *Structural Equation Modeling for Management Research Using Amos 18.0*. Bekasi: Pt Intermedia Personnelia Utama.
- 36) Hasibuan, J. S., & Silvya, B. (2019). The Effect of Work Discipline and Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Luxury Indah Jaya - Binjai. *Proceedings of the Multidisciplinary National Seminar: Product Innovation of Community Service Research & Challenges in the Era of Industrial Revolution 4.0*, 2(1), 134–147.
- 37) Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2011). *Human Resource Management*. In the revised edition of Jakarta: Bumi Aksara. Hatalea, A., Rusmiwari, S., & Aminulloh, A. (2014). Work Culture of Civil Servants. *Jisip: Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 3(2), 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.33366/Jisip.V3i2.73>
- 38) Hendayani, E. (2017). The Effect of Compensation on Employee Performance in Public Services in Jalatrang Village, Cipaku District, Ciamis Regency. *Dynamics: Scientific Journal of State Administration*, 4(4), 621–628. <https://doi.org/10.25157/Dinamika.V4i4.887>
- 39) Heri, H., & Andayani, F. (2021). The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance in the Youth Sector of the Bandung City Youth and Sports Office. *Neo Politea*, 1(2), 17–34. <https://doi.org/10.53675/Neopolitea.V1i2.105>
- 40) Hutajulu, Y. M. M., Sintani, L., & Meitiana, M. (2021). The Influence of Discipline and Work Culture on ASN Performance through the Work Motivation of Satpol PP Central Kalimantan Province. *Journal Of Environment And Management*, 2(1), 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.37304/Jem.V2i1.2658>
- 41) Jalil, A., Idris, M., & Salim, M. (2022). The Influence of Work Discipline, Work Culture and Competence on Employee Performance at the Matakali Sub-district Office, Polewali Mandar Regency. *Massaro Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Applications*, 4(2), 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.37476/Massaro.V4i2.2808>
- 42) Jufrizen, J., & Hadi, F. P. (2021). The Influence of Work Facilities and Work Discipline on Employee Performance through Work Motivation. *Journal of Management Science*, 7(1), 35–54. <https://doi.org/10.30656/Sm.V7i1.2277>

The Influence of Work Culture, Discipline, and Motivation on Employee Performance Through Competence

- 43) Head of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency. (2020). Regulation of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency Number 5 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency for 2020-2024.
- 44) Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2011). Human Resource Management. In the revised edition of Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- 45) Hatalea, A., Rusmiwari, S., & Aminulloh, A. (2014). Work Culture of Civil Servants. *Jisip: Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 3(2), 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.33366/jisip.v3i2.73>
- 46) Hendayani, E. (2017). The Effect of Compensation on Employee Performance in Public Services in Jalatrang Village, Cipaku District, Ciamis Regency. *Dynamics: Scientific Journal of State Administration*, 4(4), 621–628. <https://doi.org/10.25157/dinamika.v4i4.887>
- 47) Heri, H., & Andayani, F. (2021). The Effect of Competence on Employee Performance in the Youth Sector of the Bandung City Youth and Sports Office. *Neo Politea*, 1(2), 17–34. <https://doi.org/10.53675/Neopolitea.V1i2.105>
- 48) Hutajulu, Y. M. M., Sintani, L., & Meitiana, M. (2021). The Influence of Discipline and Work Culture on ASN Performance through the Work Motivation of Satpol PP Central Kalimantan Province. *Journal Of Environment And Management*, 2(1), 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.37304/jem.v2i1.2658>
- 49) Jalil, A., Idris, M., & Salim, M. (2022). The Influence of Work Discipline, Work Culture and Competence on Employee Performance at the Matakali Sub-district Office, Polewali Mandar Regency. *Massaro Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Applications*, 4(2), 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.37476/massaro.v4i2.2808>
- 50) Jufrizen, J., & Hadi, F. P. (2021). The Influence of Work Facilities and Work Discipline on Employee Performance through Work Motivation. *Journal of Management Science*, 7(1), 35–54. <https://doi.org/10.30656/sm.v7i1.2277>
- 51) Head of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency. (2020). Regulation of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency Number 5 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the State Cyber and Cryptography Agency for 2020-2024.
- 52) Muktamar, A., Asnawi, M., Sitepu, I., Julitasari, E. N., Djumadil, A. N., Widuri, N., Zikri, I., Damayanti, Y., & Awaliyah, F. (2024). *Fundamentals of Management* (W. Yuliani, Ed.; First, Vol. 1). Cv Hei Publishing Indonesia.
- 53) WwW.Heipublishing.Id Mulia, R. A., & Saputra, N. (2021). The Influence of Competence, Work Environment and Motivation for Achievement on the Performance of Civil Servants of the Padang City Regional Secretariat. *Scientific Journal of Ecotrans & Erudisi*, 1(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.69989/t1m78k36>
- 54) Murjani. (2022). *Quantitative Research Procedures*. Cross-Border, 5(1), 687–713.
- 55) Napitupulu, S. M. (2022). The Effect of Information Technology Utilization and Work Culture on Employee Performance with Employee Competence as an Intervening Variable in Employees of the Sriwijaya University Administration Head Office. 021008 Tridianti University Palembang.
- 56) Nawawi, H. (2001). *Human Resource Management for Competitive Business*. Gadjah Mada University Press.
- 57) Nurlita, S. (2023). The effectiveness of village government performance in realizing the vision and mission of the village head in Jaya Village, Central Kuantan District, Kuantan Singingi Regency. *Juhanperak (Journal of Law, State Administration, Sharia Banking, Accounting)*, 4(1), 1167–1186.
- 58) Ovaliana, W. D., & Mahfudz. (2022). The Effect of Online Customer Reviews and Customer Rating on Consumer Trust and Make Over Purchase Decisions on the Shopee Marketplace in Semarang City. *Diponegoro Journal Of Management*, 11(1), 1–12. <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/dbr/Acting>
- 59) Deputy for Cyber Security Operations and Cryptography. (2021). Performance Report of the Deputy for Cyber Security and Cryptography Operations for the 2021 Fiscal Year.
- 60) Prasetyo, E. T., & Marlina, P. (2019). The Effect of Work Discipline and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance. *Journal of Business and Management Inspiration*, 3(1), 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.33603/jibm.v3i1.2080>
- 61) Pratama, R. M., Lestari, R., & Nurleli. (2022). The Effect of the Application of Human Resource Management Practices on Competitive Advantage. *NCAF (Proceedings Of National Conference On Accounting & Finance)*, 4(1), 313–322. <https://doi.org/10.20885/ncaf.vol4.art39>
- 62) Gandung, M. (2021). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Kinerja Dan Prilaku Berorganisasi* (Vol. 1). CV. AA. RIZKY.
- 63) Gandung, M. (2022). The Effect of Work Supervision and Discipline on Employee Performance at PT. Personel Alih Daya (Persero) Jakarta Selatan. *International Journal of Education, Information Technology, and Others*, 5(2), 10-24.